

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON EDUCATION, ECONOMY AND SOCIETY

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Abstract

Dealing with the unforeseen challenges caused by the Covid-19 pandemic has taken a significant toll on people all across the world. The economic and social destructions caused by the pandemic is devastating. This paper helps to understand the impact of covid 19 on economy, society and education. The researcher found that pandemic has a far reaching impact on Indian economy and society. Online teaching learning process encourages students to think and learn deeply and prepare for the future world.

Keywords: Covid-19, Economy, Education, Society

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Introduction:

“No pandemic is ever just a health issue in isolation, and Covid-19 has emphasised this on the global stage. We need to be looking at it in terms of economic issue, a livelihood issue, a social issue and a political issue too” stated by Juliet Bedford, Anthropologist.

The Covid-19 has led a huge loss of human life worldwide and created a great threat to human health and the work life. The economic and social destructions caused by the pandemic is devastating. As we are aware that India is a developing economy, our economy is passing through demand depression and high unemployment, with 68-days long hard lockdown announced by Prime Minister Modi on March 23, 2020, it slow downed the supply-side, accelerating the slowdown further and harming the economic wellbeing of millions.

Businesses are coping with lost revenue and interrupted supply chain as factory shutdowns and quarantine measures spread across the globe which restricting movements and commerce. Around millions of people are at risk of falling down below the poverty line and compel to live malnourished life.

Women have been harder hit economically during this period because they are a large proportion of the workers in sectors severely affected by Covid-19 like accommodation and food services. To slow down the spread of virus schools also closed all over the world. This also added an extra burden on girl child as they have to bear extra responsibilities at home. Even working women struggled lots while maintaining balance between the office work and house chores.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the current covid 19 situation in India.

- To study the influence of covid 19 on economy and society.
- To study the impact of covid 19 on education.
- To draw the conclusion of the study.

Significance of the Study

The study will help to understand the severity of covid 19 in India. Covid 19 has disturbed the life cycle of humans and compelled them to make changes in their working as well as living patterns. The research will help to understand the impact of covid 19 on Indian economy by taking into account different sectors in India.

The study exhibits the far reaching impacts of a deadly virus on education system and society which changed the lives of many people upside down.

Hypothesis for the study

The statement of hypothesis for the study is “Online education system has a positive impact on the learning process of undergraduate level students”.

Research Methodology

The study is based on the primary as well as secondary data. The data has been collected through questionnaire from 105 students at the undergraduate level from Thane. The data has been analysed with percentage method.

The secondary data is collected from different websites, reports and research papers. The data has been presented with the help of tables and graphs.

Review of Literature

Barbate Vikas, Gade Rajesh and Raibagkar Shirish¹ has stated that Covid 19 is the biggest hit to Indian economy. To overcome such crisis all stakeholders need to join hands. It's not the sole responsibility of government to revive economy.

Singh Jaspreet and Singh Jagandeep² has studied the impact of covid 19 on human life and society. Social connections and interactions are the integral part of human life. They revealed that social distancing created loneliness, stressful life, anxiety, health disorder etc.

Jena Pravat Kumar³ has revealed that around 32 crores learners stopped to move schools. The paper is about measures taken by Indian government to provide seamless education in India. Pandemic forced education system to grow and use technology which has not been used before.

Impact of Covid-19 on Indian Economy and Society

Dealing with the unforeseen challenges caused by the Covid-19 pandemic has taken a significant toll on people all across the world. It has disturbed not only human life but also material world.

Economic impacts

Sector wise impact of Covid-19:

- Agriculture – During pandemic farmers face challenges in terms of their livelihood. Due to the lockdown, farmers are unable to sell their crops, many markets are still closed. In addition to this, the men in the family are currently stuck in Mumbai where they work, so there are no other people to help the women in the household in bringing their crops home.
- Since workers are not available, they cannot seek help elsewhere. If this situation persists then possibility to revive India's economy will be severely affected.

- Textile – Production halts in China have had an impact on this sector as we depend on China for textile raw materials including synthetic yarn, synthetic fabric, buttons, zippers, and hangers. India also exports cotton yarn to China in bulk quantity, and poor demand in China has caused cotton prices to come down in India.
- Automotive – Current pandemic situation has deteriorated the situation as China accounts for 27 percent of India's automotive part imports. Wuhan is a major auto hub. Due to the lockdown in Wuhan the supply chain of the automotive sector has been hit significantly.
- Aviation – Due to increasing numbers of Covid-19 cases global travel is suspended. Airlines are looking at bankruptcy. As revenue streams drying up, companies will be forced to restructure their workforce.
- Hotels and restaurants – The pandemic has brought the hotel sector in India to its knees. The Indian hotels sector has been hit hard, occupancy across hotels in key cities declined rapidly. The overall revenue of the Indian hotel sector is set to decline by anywhere between US\$8.85 billion to US\$ 10 billion represents decline of 30% to 45 % compared to last year.
- Poultry – Due to false claims regarding transmission of Covid-19 through chicken and other meat have impacted the sales and price of poultry items.
- Pharmaceuticals – During coronavirus pandemic lockdown badly affected all major sectors of the economy, but it has come as a boon in disguise to the Indian pharmaceutical sector. The medicine spending in India is expected to grow between 9-12 per cent over the next five years, leading India to become one of the top 10 countries in terms of medical spending.
- E-Commerce – E-commerce players are unable to service existing orders and are not accepting new orders, even when there is a huge demand for home delivery. But companies are trying to service essential items on priority basis.
- IT - Remote working has given rise in demand for communication tools, conference platforms, and cyber security apps. These software tools are being used across sectors such as education, finance, and HR to ensure business continuity.
- Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) – The Covid impact is felt acutely in the consumer durable sector as it has a high dependency on China for imports. India majorly imports a bulk of its consumer durables components and completely built units of consumer durables from China.

Social Impacts:

Covid-19 has had massive impact on Social life of human beings. Some of the impacts are:

- Social distancing and self-isolation
- Travel restrictions
- School closure
- Disruption of normal life of children
- Spread of panic and fear through social media
- Poor people, homeless people, refugees, migrants are disproportionately affected by the health and economic impacts of COVID
- Decreased demand for commodities and manufactured products
- Created socio-psychological issues.

Increased inequalities and gender disparities in society.

Impact of online education system on undergraduate level students during Covid-19 No one has full control over the things happening around us. The virus has not left any place untouched. The pandemic time has left a memorable impact in the field of education. By the end of March 2020 government declared closure of schools, colleges and universities in India to slow down the spread of virus. This has opened a gate for innovative ways of disseminating knowledge to students.

It draws the attention of researcher to study the impact of online method in learning process. The study is about analysing the effectiveness of online teaching learning mechanism during covid 19. For the survey purpose primary data has been collected from 105 participants through questionnaire.

Table 1
Impact of online education system during Covid-19

Sr. No.	Particulars	Yes (%)	No (%)	Can't say (%)
1	Do students find this online teaching boring after the initial exposure?	56.19%	29.52%	14.29%
2	Do you think tech helps to make teaching and learning process more interesting?	51.43%	34.29%	14.29%
3	Do you think the modern method of teaching via technology is better than the traditional method via chalk board?	35.24%	50.48%	14.29%
4	Does the usage of technology lead to frustration and non-productivity?	40.95%	44.76%	14.29%
5	Does this tech help to prepare students for the modern world?	58.10%	27.62%	14.29%
6	Are you satisfied with the current online teaching learning process?	31.43%	54.29%	14.29%

(Source: Primary data)

Graph 1

Impact of online education system during Covid-19

(Source: Primary data)

From the above table and graph it showed that about 56.19 per cent students found online platform to educate students was boring in initial exposure and about 29.52 per cent students thought vice versa. Around 14.29 per cent preferred not to say anything. Further it was observed that about 51.43 per cent students felt technology made teaching learning process more interesting and about 34.29 per cent vice versa. The research showed that around 50.48 per cent students considered the traditional method of teaching was better than modern one and around 35.24 per cent vice versa. The analysis showed that around 40.95 per cent felt technology led to non-productivity and around 44.76 per cent vice versa. The study depicted that around 58.1 per cent students thought it helped students to prepare for the modern world and around 27.62 per cent vice versa. It was observed that approximately 31.43 per cent students were satisfied with current online teaching and around 54.29 per cent vice versa.

On the basis of analysis it concluded that in the initial stage students were not happy with the online method. Indian students are habitual of offline education system. Sudden outbreak of pandemic didn't give time to students to accept such changes. Gradually they adapted such changes and started taking interest in online sessions. Though they believe modern method will make them competent enough poor network, technical issues lead to frustration and non-productivity in case of some of the students. Overall impact of online method is negative. Majority of the students are not satisfied with it. Thus hypothesis is rejected.

Findings

- Indian economy has faced downfall during pandemic as country was shut down for some days. This disturbed the whole economy.
- Social distancing created social psychological issues for humans.

- Indian education system is mainly based on the traditional classroom method. Neither faculties nor students were prepared for the situation. So when it was introduced in the system students were reluctant to accept such drastical change from the school based learning to the online mode.

Conclusion

Large number of industries face an extreme threat. Millions of population is at risk of losing their livelihoods. It has disturbed different industrial sectors which has hampered the growth of Indian economy. During pandemic major chunk of unemployed is covered by women. So it has created gender disparities. Due to social distancing, restrictions on travelling loosen the social ties of humans.

Online learning is an effective medium of delivering knowledge to geographically dispersed students. Online teaching learning process definitely encourage them to think and learn deeply, feeling it is an interesting way of learning. But it will take some time for faculties to learn how to use technology to make sessions more interesting as well as students to accept such changes.

Pandemic has brought a lot of changes in economy, society and education sector which certainly compelled humans to push their limits while facing such changes.

Suggestions

- Indian manufacturers has an opportunity to emerge as suppliers and reduce the dependency on China.
- During pandemic everyone needs to remember a human touch and provide an emotional support to each other during crisis.
- Presence of technology in life is inevitable. Thus teachers must use different innovative teachings techniques such as videos, quiz, extempore, group discussion to make teaching learning process more interesting and make their students stronger to face the challenges in the world.
- Despite of several positive facts learning through technology makes us more dependent on it which leads to health issues and mental stress. So it should be used but up to limited extent.

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